

**ORIENTIRLANMAGAN KO'PXILLIKDA SILLIQ
AKSLANTIRISHLARNING GOMOTOP BO'LISHI**

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ANNOTATSIYA

Mazkur maqolada orientirlanmagan ko'pxilliklarda silliq akslantirishlarning gomotop bo'lishi haqidagi masala qo'yilgan. Bunda dastlab, silliq akslantirish, bog'lanishli va bog'lanishsiz to'plamlar, Yakobi matritsasi, silliq gomotopiya va orientirlanmagan ko'pxilliklar tushunchalari keltirilgan. Maqolada asosiy masala orientirlanmagan ko'pxillikda akslantirishlarning darajalari qanday holda teng bo'lishligi isbotlangan.

Kalit so'zlar: silliq akslantirish, gomotopiya, orientirlanmagan, mod2 va akslantirish darajasi.

**ГОМОТОПИЧЕСКОЕ РАЗДЕЛЕНИЕ ГЛАДКИХ ОТРАЖЕНИЙ В
НЕОРИЕНТИРОВАННОМ МНОЖЕСТВЕ**

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АННОТАЦИЯ

В статье рассматривается вопрос о гомотопии гладких отражений в неориентированных многообразиях. Во-первых, представлены понятия гладкого отражения, связанных и несвязных множеств, матрицы Якоби, гладких гомотопических и неориентированных многообразий. Основной вопрос статьи

— как доказать равенство уровней отражений в неориентированной множественности.

Ключевые слова: гладкое отражение, гомотопия, неориентированность, mod2, уровень отражения.

HOMOTOPIC PARTITION OF SMOOTH REFLECTIONS IN AN UNORIENTED MULTIPLY

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ANNOTATION

This article deals with the issue of homotopy of smooth reflections in non-oriented manifolds. First, the concepts of smooth reflection, connected and unconnected sets, Jacobi matrix, smooth homotopy and unoriented manifolds are presented. The main issue in the article is how to prove that the levels of reflections are equal in an unoriented multiplicity.

Keywords: smooth reflection, homotopy, unoriented, mod2, and reflection level.

Kirish

Bizga $f : N \rightarrow M$ silliq akslantirish berilgan bo'lib, N va M lar kompakt, bog'lanishli, orientirlangan, yopiq ko'pxilliklar bo'lib, ularning o'lchamlari teng bo'lsin: $\dim N = \dim M$. Agar f akslantirishning Q nuqtadagi Yakobi matritsasining

determinanti $\det J\left(\frac{\partial f}{\partial x_i}\right) > 0$ bo'lsa, $Q \in f^{-1}(p)$ uchun $\varepsilon(Q) = +1$ olamiz,

$\det J\left(\frac{\partial f}{\partial x_i}\right) < 0$ bo'lsa, $\varepsilon(Q) = -1$ olamiz.

1-ta’rif. Agar f_1, f_2, \dots, f_m uzluksiz va r –tartibgacha uzluksiz xususiy hosilalarga ega bo’lsa ($r \geq 1$). f akslantirish C^r akslantirish yoki silliq akslantirish deyiladi.

Quyidagi matritsa f akslantirishning Yakobi matritsasi deb ataladi:

$$J(f) = \begin{pmatrix} \frac{\partial f_1}{\partial x_1} & \frac{\partial f_1}{\partial x_2} & \dots & \frac{\partial f_1}{\partial x_n} \\ \frac{\partial f_2}{\partial x_1} & \frac{\partial f_2}{\partial x_2} & \dots & \frac{\partial f_2}{\partial x_n} \\ \dots & \dots & \dots & \dots \\ \frac{\partial f_m}{\partial x_1} & \frac{\partial f_m}{\partial x_2} & \dots & \frac{\partial f_m}{\partial x_n} \end{pmatrix}$$

(X, τ) topologik fazo, $A \subset X$ – qism to’plam bo’lsin.

2-ta’rif. Ikkita ochiq U va V qism to’plamlar mavjud bo’lib,

- a) $A = (A \cap U) \cup (A \cap V)$
- b) $(A \cap U) \cap (A \cap V) = \emptyset$
- c) $A \cap U \neq \emptyset, A \cap V \neq \emptyset$

shart bajarilsa, A to’plam bog’lanishsiz to’plam deyiladi. Agar bu shartlarni qanoatlantiruvchi U va V ochiq to’plamlar mavjud bo’lmasa, A to’plam bog’lanishli to’plam deyiladi.

3-ta’rif. f akslantirishning $p \in M$ regulyar nuqtadagi darajasi deb $\deg_p f = \sum_{Q \in f^{-1}(p)} \varepsilon(Q)$ songa aytiladi.

4-ta’rif. f akslantirishning silliq gomotopiyasi deb, $F: N \times I \rightarrow M$ ($I = [0, 1]$) silindirni akslantiruvchi $(x, 0) = f(x)$, $\forall x \in N$ uchun o’rinli bo’ladigan silliq F akslantirishga aytiladi.

Ayta olamizki, $f_t: N \rightarrow M$, $f_t(x) = F(x, t)$ akslantirishlar boshlang’ich $f = f_0$ akslantirishga gomotop, silindirni akslantiruvchi barcha F lar gomotopiya deb ataladi.

Akslantirish darajasi ko'pxillik orientirlanmagan holda ham aniqlangan bo'lib, yakobianlarning ishoralari bu yerda invariant ma'noga ega bo'lmaydi. Shuning uchun akslantirish darajasi mod 2 bo'yicha aniqlanadi.

Asosiy qism

Teorema. Ikkita silliq $f, g: N \rightarrow S^n$ akslantirishlar yopiq n -o'lchamli orientirlanmagan ko'pxillikni n -o'lchamli sferaga o'tkazsin. Bu akslantirishlar gomotop bo'lishi uchun ularning darajalari mod 2 bo'yicha ustma-ust tushishi zarur va yetarli.

Isbot. Zarurligi. Aytaylik f va g akslantirishlar gomotop bo'lsin. Unda biz ularning akslantirish darajalari tengligini ko'rsataylik, ya'ni $\deg f = \deg g$.

Faraz qilaylik $f^{-1}(y)$ m ta proobrazga ega bo'lsin: x_1, x_2, \dots, x_m . Ko'pxillik orientirlanmaganligi uchun Yakobi matritsasining determinanti nol, ya'ni $\det J\left(\frac{\partial f}{\partial x_i}\right) = 0$ bo'ladigan nuqtalar soni k_1 ta bo'lsin. Xuddi shunday $g^{-1}(y)$ n ta proobrazga ega bo'lsin: x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n . Bunda ham Yakobi matritsasining determinanti nol, ya'ni $\det J\left(\frac{\partial f}{\partial x_i}\right) = 0$ bo'ladigan nuqtalar soni k_2 ta bo'lsin. Shu bilan birga f va g akslantirishlar gomotop bo'lganligi uchun $m - k_1$ va $n - k_2$ nuqtalar soni bir vaqtda yoki juft yoki toq bo'lsin. Unda $m - k_1 \equiv n - k_2 \pmod{2}$ bo'ladi, ya'ni bu ikki akslantirishlarning proobrazlardagi nuqtalar sonini ikkiga bo'lgandagi qoldig'i bir vaqtda yoki nol yoki birga teng bo'ladi. Bundan kelib chiqadiki, f va g akslantirishlarning darajalari ustma-ust tushadi.

Yetarliligi. Faraz qilaylik f va g akslantirishlarning darajalari teng bo'lsin. Unda f akslantirishni $f^{-1}(y_0)$ va $g^{-1}(y_0)$ proobrazlar aniq ustma-ust tushadigan qilib deformatsiyalaymiz.

Boshqa tomondan f akslantirishni shunday akslantirishga deformatsiyalaymizki, u akslantirishning differensial g akslantirishning differensial bilan $f^{-1}(y_0) = g^{-1}(y_0)$ to'liq proobrazning har bir nuqtasida ustma-ust tushsin.

Endi y_0 nuqtaning $\varepsilon > 0$ atrofini qaraylik. Bu atrofda ikkala f va g akslantirishlarning y_0 nuqtadagi barcha proobrazlarining atroflarida shunday deformatsiyalaymizki, ularning ε -atrofdagi lokal koordinatalar sistemasiga nisbatan f va g akslantirishlar chiziqli bo'lib qolsin. Bunda ε -atroflarning obrazlari S^n sferaga diffeomorf joylashadi, Ularning chegaralari esa y_0 nuqtaga qarama-qarshi nuqtaga o'tsin. ε -atroflarning to'ldiruvchilarining barchasini shu nuqtaga o'tadi deb hisoblashimiz mumkin. Shunday qilib, y_0 nuqtaning S^n sferadagi to'ldiruvchisini R^n -Yevklid fazosi bo'ladi. Bu deformatsiyalardan keyin f va g akslantirishlar ustma-ust tushadi. Teorema isbotlandi.

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